

The Holst (Immirzi) parameter γ in loop quantum gravity (LQG): A statistical estimation of the numerical value

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Abstract

Loop quantum gravity (LQG) is a theory built on the quantization of the Holst action, which displays an unconstrained coupling constant, known as the Holst (Immirzi) parameter γ . In the literature many strategies have been pursued to tackle the parameter freedom. Here, inspired by the 1930s Bronstein argument, the approach is to probe the space of general relativity (GR) with a progressively localized quantum object, in particular a Gaussian photon. The aim is to detect a discontinuity in the classical space to be related to the discrete quantum space outlined in LQG. By comparing the geometric properties of both, we constrain the arbitrarily free parameter γ within a tight interval of values, that is: $0.2256 \approx < \gamma < \approx 0.2887$. Interesting to note, the statistical range covers strictly the numerical values provided by the black hole event horizon SU(2) microstates counting methodology in the literature, which are the solidified choice for a real γ in canonical LQG.

1 Introduction

Loop quantum gravity (LQG) is a background-independent quantization of the gravitational field, as described by general relativity (GR) in four dimensions, refer to [1]. The starting point to construct the theory is the Holst model, which is classically equivalent to GR. The Holst action exhibits a coupling constant, known as the Holst (Immirzi) parameter γ , which is left free by the theory. The parameter does not affect the classical description, but plays a substantial role in the quantum picture, in particular touching the geometric properties of space.

In the literature many strategies have been proposed to tackle the parameter freedom. We will come back later on that. Here the idea is to investigate the

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space of GR with a progressively localized quantum object in order to challenge its classical smoothness. If we single out a discontinuity in the classical space, we can compare its geometric properties to the discrete quantum space, as sketched by LQG, thus constraining the γ parameter.

In the next sections we present the theoretical apparatus to conduct this conceptual experiment.

2 Holst action

The Holst formulation of GR is a frame-affine formulation, that is a field theory based on a spin frame (tetrads) and an independent connection, depending on a real adimensional parameter γ , not further constrained. Referring to [2], the Holst action in dimension 4 shows as

$$A_H = \frac{1}{2\kappa} \int_D \left(\frac{1}{2} R^{IJ} \wedge e^K \wedge e^L \epsilon_{IJKL} + \frac{1}{\gamma} R^{IJ} \wedge e_I \wedge e_J - \frac{\Lambda}{12} e^I \wedge e^J \wedge e^K \wedge e^L \epsilon_{IJKL} \right) \quad (1)$$

where:

A_H Holst action

$$\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^3}$$

D spacetime integration region

$$R^{IJ} = d\omega^{IJ} + \omega_K^I \wedge \omega^{KJ} = \frac{1}{2} R_{\mu\nu}^{IJ} dx^\mu \wedge dx^\nu \quad \text{curvature 2-form}$$

$$\omega^{IJ} = \omega_\mu^{IJ} dx^\mu \quad \text{connection 1-form}$$

ω_μ^{IJ} Spin(3,1) connection

$$R_{\mu\nu}^{IJ} = \partial_\mu \omega_\nu^{IJ} - \partial_\nu \omega_\mu^{IJ} + \omega_{K\mu}^I \omega_\nu^{KJ} - \omega_{K\nu}^I \omega_\mu^{KJ} \quad \text{curvature}$$

$$e^I = e_\mu^I dx^\mu \quad \text{coframe 1-form}$$

e_μ^I spin coframe

ϵ_{IJKL} Levi-Civita tensor

γ Holst (Immirzi) parameter

Λ cosmological constant

3 Quantum geometry at the ground state

Let us consider a simple geometric object, for instance a tetrahedron. According to LQG, refer to [1], the fundamental quantum state of a tetrahedron T , that is its ground state, characterized by each face labeled by a minimum spin $j = \frac{1}{2}$, presents the following geometric properties

$$\begin{aligned} Area_T &= 16\sqrt{3}\pi\gamma l_{Pl}^2 \\ Volume_T &= \frac{(8\pi)^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\sqrt{6\sqrt{3}}}\gamma^{\frac{3}{2}} l_{Pl}^3 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where:

l_{Pl} Planck length

4 Black hole solution in general relativity (GR)

The Schwarzschild solution to the Einstein field equations of GR describes a gravitational field outside a spherical distribution of matter. Referring to [3], a particular geometry of spacetime occurs when the relation between the mass m of the gravitating object and the radial coordinate r is such that

$$\frac{2Gm}{c^2r} = 1 \tag{3}$$

This peculiar configuration is known as a black hole (BH) and the radial coordinate, or Schwarzschild radius, indicates the event horizon, that is the surface which hides the interior of the black hole from the exterior region of spacetime.

5 Probing the space of GR with a photon

In order to probe the space of GR at small distances, we get inspiration from an argument proposed in 1936 by the Russian theoretical physicist M. P. Bronstein, refer to [1]. To mark a location we need a particle at that position, however a particle is a quantum object and according to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, which states $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$, refer to [4], the uncertainty in position Δx is inversely proportional to the uncertainty in momentum Δp . That is a well known consequence of the Heisenberg uncertainty relation: a sharper localization requires a larger momentum. In turn, a larger momentum implies a larger energy. Now, according to special relativity (SR), there is an equivalence relation between mass and energy, the famous $E = mc^2$, refer to [5], hence any form of energy acts as a gravitating object and, according to GR, distorts the spacetime around it. The distortion increases with the energy concentration until a black hole forms, refer to equation (3), so that the portion of space to localize becomes hidden beyond an event horizon and thus localization is lost. Therefore, combining quantum mechanics (QM) and GR, we can localize only up to a minimum chunk of space, that we may compare to the ground state of space as envisaged by LQG.

The ideal candidate to explore the space of GR is a photon, whose wave function is described by a Gaussian wave packet. In fact a Gaussian profile satisfies the Heisenberg uncertainty relation with an equality, that is $\Delta x \Delta p = \hbar/2$, thus ensuring a minimum uncertainty, refer to [4]. A Gaussian photon displays the following characteristics

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta x & \text{ position uncertainty} \\
p & \text{ average momentum} \\
\Delta p & \text{ momentum uncertainty} \\
\Delta x = \frac{\hbar}{2\Delta p} & \text{ Gaussian profile}
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Moreover from SR, refer to [5], we have for a photon

$$E = pc \quad \text{average energy} \tag{5}$$

As per equation (4), in order to localize, we need a large momentum uncertainty, however not arbitrarily large. In fact a momentum uncertainty reaching over negative values of the Gaussian momentum profile would be questionable for a physical wave packet. Hence we may regard the one standard deviation (1σ) approximation congruent to the average momentum as the largest physically meaningful uncertainty in momentum. Nevertheless we can not neglect that a 1σ approximation corresponds to a confidence level of 68.3 %, refer to [6], leaving uncovered a non irrelevant part of the momentum spread. To improve the coverage we may consider the 2σ and 3σ approximations as well.

Let us define the $n\sigma$ approximation

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta p &= \frac{p}{n} \\
\Delta x &= \frac{n\hbar}{2p} \\
r &= n\Delta x \\
p &= \frac{n^2\hbar}{2r}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where:

$n = 1, 2, 3$ approximation level

r BH radius

Considering the $n\sigma$ momentum, equation (6), the energy-momentum relation of a photon, equation (5), the mass-energy equivalence and plugging all this in the BH condition, equation (3), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
r_{BH} &= nl_{Pl} && \text{BH radius} \\
Area_{BH} &= 4\pi r_{BH}^2 = 4\pi n^2 l_{Pl}^2 && \text{BH area} \\
Volume_{BH} &= \frac{4}{3}\pi r_{BH}^3 = \frac{4}{3}\pi n^3 l_{Pl}^3 && \text{BH volume} \\
p_{BH} &= \frac{n^2 \hbar}{2r_{BH}} = \frac{1}{2} n p_{Pl} && \text{BH momentum} \\
E_{BH} &= p_{BH} c = \frac{1}{2} n E_{Pl} && \text{BH energy} \\
\epsilon_{BH} &= \frac{E_{BH}}{Volume_{BH}} = \frac{3}{8\pi n^2} \epsilon_{Pl} && \text{BH energy density}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where:

$n = 1, 2, 3$ *approximation level*
 l_{Pl} *Planck length*
 p_{Pl} *Planck momentum*
 E_{Pl} *Planck energy*
 ϵ_{Pl} *Planck energy density*

6 Geometric properties comparison

Now, on one hand we have the fundamental quantum tetrahedron (ground state) from LQG, on the other hand we have the minimum physically significant region of space from a combination of QM and GR. We expect them to agree. So, let us compare their geometric properties, that is area and volume.

By comparing the fundamental quantum tetrahedron geometric properties, equation (2), against the BH geometric properties, equation (7), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{area, n\sigma} &= \frac{1}{4\sqrt{3}} n^2 \approx 0.1443 n^2 \\
\gamma_{volume, n\sigma} &= \frac{1}{2(2\sqrt{3}\pi)^{\frac{1}{3}}} n^2 \approx 0.2256 n^2
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where:

$n = 1, 2, 3$ *approximation level*
 $n\sigma$ *confidence level*

7 Constraining the γ parameter spread

Clearly the detection of a discontinuity in space via a quantum object, that is a fuzzy entity, resulted in a (Gaussian) statistical estimation of the γ parameter.

Nevertheless, we can reduce noticeably the spread if we ask the evaluation to adhere to the following requirements:

- As we are looking for a minimum chunk of space, we have to stay as close as possible to the 1σ approximation.
- As we compare the geometric properties of the fundamental quantum tetrahedron and the minimum black hole, we demand the consequent values of the parameter to comply, hence we privilege the overlapping values between the area and volume intervals.

As per above, we notice that the 1σ approximation provides only two single and different values for the parameter. There is no overlapping. Instead the 2σ approximation offers two intervals of values which overlap. That is what we were looking for. Moreover, as per the first point above, we should emphasize the much lower part of the overlap. All this can be encoded as

$$0.2256 \approx < \textit{(less than)} \gamma \textit{(much less than)} \ll \approx 0.5774 \quad (9)$$

The statement as per equation (9) raises the question about a possible upper bound of the much lower part of the overlap. To answer, heuristically we can try an intermediate approximation, the $m\sigma/n\sigma$ approximation, defined as the $m\sigma$ approximation in momentum space, the $n\sigma$ approximation in position space and symmetric in m, n , that is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p &= \frac{p}{m} \\ \Delta x &= \frac{m\hbar}{2p} \\ r &= n\Delta x \\ p &= \frac{mn\hbar}{2r} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where:

$m, n = 1, 2, 3$ *approximation level in momentum space/position space*

r *BH radius*

Considering the $m\sigma/n\sigma$ momentum, equation (10), the energy-momentum relation of a photon, equation (5), the mass-energy equivalence and plugging all this in the BH condition, equation (3), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
r_{BH} &= \sqrt{mn}l_{Pl} && \text{BH radius} \\
Area_{BH} &= 4\pi r_{BH}^2 = 4\pi mn l_{Pl}^2 && \text{BH area} \\
Volume_{BH} &= \frac{4}{3}\pi r_{BH}^3 = \frac{4}{3}\pi(mn)^{\frac{3}{2}}l_{Pl}^3 && \text{BH volume} \\
p_{BH} &= \frac{mn\hbar}{2r_{BH}} = \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{mn}p_{Pl} && \text{BH momentum} \\
E_{BH} &= p_{BH}c = \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{mn}E_{Pl} && \text{BH energy} \\
\epsilon_{BH} &= \frac{E_{BH}}{Volume_{BH}} = \frac{3}{8\pi mn}\epsilon_{Pl} && \text{BH energy density}
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where:

$m, n = 1, 2, 3$ approximation level in momentum space/position space

l_{Pl} Planck length

p_{Pl} Planck momentum

E_{Pl} Planck energy

ϵ_{Pl} Planck energy density

By comparing the fundamental quantum tetrahedron geometric properties, equation (2), against the BH geometric properties in the $m\sigma/n\sigma$ approximation, equation (11), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{area, m\sigma/n\sigma} &= \frac{1}{4\sqrt{3}}mn \approx 0.1443mn \\
\gamma_{volume, m\sigma/n\sigma} &= \frac{1}{2(2\sqrt{3}\pi)^{\frac{1}{3}}}mn \approx 0.2256mn
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where:

$m, n = 1, 2, 3$ approximation level in momentum space/position space

$m\sigma/n\sigma$ confidence level in momentum space/position space

The $2\sigma/1\sigma$ approximation is the minimum approximation allowing for an overlapping between the area and volume intervals, thus coding the essence of the statistical approach as

$$0.2256 \approx < \gamma < \approx 0.2887 \tag{13}$$

8 Estimations of the γ parameter in the literature

In the literature there is not a single universally agreed numerical value of the Holst (Immirzi) parameter γ . Different arguments give different values. Here below we briefly present different methodologies, in particular the procedures that yield a value anyhow.

Quasinormal modes (QNM)

Hod (1998), refer to [7], applied Bohr’s correspondence principle to the asymptotic quasinormal modes (QNM) frequency of a Schwarzschild black hole to infer the minimal area change. Dreyer (2003), refer to [8], matched this to the LQG area spectrum assuming a minimal spin j_{min} . For $j_{min} = 1$, implying an $SO(3)$ gauge group, it gives $\gamma \approx 0.1236$.

Corichi (2003), refer to [9], reexamined the identification between QNM area spacing and the LQG area spectrum. He argued that Dreyer’s assumption of the minimal spin was unnecessary and inconsistent with the $SU(2)$ structure of LQG. However he did not dismiss the j_{min} by Dreyer. Had he restored $j_{min} = \frac{1}{2}$, that would have yielded $\gamma \approx 0.2019$.

$SU(2)$ microstates counting (Canonical LQG)

Ashtekar, Baez, Corichi and Krasnov (1998), refer to [10], Ashtekar, Baez and Krasnov (2000), refer to [11], derived the black hole entropy from LQG using the newly developed framework of isolated horizons. The horizon is treated as an internal boundary in canonical LQG and quantization of boundary degrees of freedom leads to a $U(1)$ Chern–Simons theory on the horizon. The bulk geometry is encoded in spin network edges puncturing the horizon, each labeled by spins j_i contributing discrete area quanta. Microstates correspond to assignments of magnetic numbers m_i satisfying a global $U(1)$ charge neutrality constraint (projection constraint). Counting these states yields an entropy proportional to the horizon area for large black holes. Requiring the Bekenstein–Hawking law fixes the parameter as $\gamma \approx 0.1274$.

Domagała and Lewandowski (2004), refer to [12], revisited black hole entropy in LQG using the full $SU(2)$ gauge invariant counting of horizon microstates rather than earlier $U(1)$ reduced methods. By imposing the isolated horizon boundary conditions and counting admissible spin configurations that satisfy the area constraint, they derived an entropy–area relation for large areas that matched to the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy law, thus bounding the parameter as $0.2206 \approx \gamma < \approx 0.3497$.

Meissner (2004), refer to [13], refined the $SU(2)$ black hole microstates counting initiated by Domagała and Lewandowski. He solved the combinatorial problem analytically using generating functions to count all spin configurations contributing to a given horizon area, ensuring exact implementation of the projection constraint. By requiring the entropy to match the Bekenstein–Hawking law for large black holes he fixed $\gamma \approx 0.2375$.

Ghosh and Mitra (2005), refer to [14], reanalyzed black hole entropy in LQG by improving the statistical treatment of horizon microstates and carefully enforcing the projection constraint on total spin. They considered the full $SU(2)$ spectrum and examined how different assumptions about the ensemble of punctures affect the entropy–area relation. By demanding consistency with the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy, they obtained a slightly different value from earlier works, that is $\gamma \approx 0.274$, a value depending weakly on the counting scheme and the choice of minimal spin $j_{min} = \frac{1}{2}$. Their analysis highlighted the sensitivity of γ to statistical and combinatorial details in the horizon state counting.

Engle, Noui, Perez and Pranzetti (2010), refer to [15], reformulated black hole entropy in LQG using a fully $SU(2)$ invariant treatment of type I isolated horizons, avoiding the older $U(1)$ reduction. They quantized the horizon degrees of freedom as an $SU(2)$ Chern–Simons theory with punctures carrying spin representations j_i and counted microstates consistent with the area constraint. They confirmed the previous value of $\gamma \approx 0.274$.

Analytic continuation/self-dual approach

Frodden, Geiller, Noui and Perez (2014), refer to [16], Jibril, Mouchet and Noui (2015), refer to [17], analytically continued the black hole entropy calculation and spinfoam amplitudes to self-dual complex Ashtekar variables, taking $\gamma = \pm i$. In this framework the Bekenstein–Hawking law emerges strikingly in the large spin semiclassical limit, without tuning a real γ . Hence no numerical real value is fixed. The favorite interpretation is that γ should be purely imaginary (self-dual) rather than a physical real constant.

Barbero and Pranzetti (2022), refer to [18], give an account of the state of the art about black hole entropy in LQG. They provide a historical summary and explain how black hole entropy is described by relying on the concept of isolated horizon, with an emphasis on different representations of its associated symmetry group. They continue with a review of the combinatorial methods necessary to understand the behavior of the entropy as a function of the area and conclude with a discussion of the nature of the quantum horizon degrees of freedom that account for the black hole entropy and the related issue of fixing the parameter γ .

A comment about the analytic continuation/self-dual approach. As the resulting γ is complex (imaginary)-valued, that is conflicting with the requirements for the action in physics. The action should be real-valued to ensure the theory respects unitarity, i.e. physically meaningful probabilities. Therefore we will disregard that outcome from the literature.

9 Conclusions

Ideally probing the space of GR with a progressively localized quantum object, specifically a Gaussian photon, detected a discontinuity in space at small distances to be regarded as the minimum physically significant region of space. If we relate this minimum portion of space to the fundamental quantum tetrahedron (ground state) featured in LQG and compare the geometric properties of both, we constrain the arbitrarily free Holst (Immirzi) parameter γ of LQG within a tight interval of values, refer to equation (13), stated here again: $0.2256 \approx < \gamma < \approx 0.2887$.

It is interesting to note that the statistical range covers strictly the numerical values provided by the black hole event horizon $SU(2)$ microstates counting methodology in the literature, which are the solidified choice for a real γ in

canonical LQG.

Appendix

A.1 Acronyms

BH black hole
 GR general relativity
 LQG loop quantum gravity
 QM quantum mechanics
 QNM quasinormal modes
 SR special relativity
 T tetrahedron

A.2 Fundamental constants

$$c = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1} \quad \textit{speed of light}$$

$$G = 6.67428(67) \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2} \quad \textit{gravitational constant}$$

$$\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi} = 1.054571628(53) \times 10^{-34} \text{ J s} \quad \textit{reduced Planck constant}$$

$$k_B = 1.380649 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1} \quad \textit{Boltzmann constant}$$

Source: [3]

A.3 Planck units

$$l_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}} = 1.616252(81) \times 10^{-35} \text{ m} \quad \textit{Planck length}$$

$$t_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}} = 5.39124(27) \times 10^{-44} \text{ s} \quad \textit{Planck time}$$

$$m_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}} = 2.17644(11) \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg} \quad \textit{Planck mass}$$

$$p_{Pl} = m_{Pl}c = \frac{\hbar}{l_{Pl}} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^3}{G}} = 6.52485 \text{ kg m s}^{-1} \quad \textit{Planck momentum}$$

$$E_{Pl} = m_{Pl}c^2 = \frac{\hbar}{t_{Pl}} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G}} = 1.961 \times 10^9 \text{ J} = 1.22 \times 10^{19} \text{ GeV} \quad \textit{Planck energy}$$

$$\epsilon_{Pl} = \frac{E_{Pl}}{l_{Pl}^3} = \frac{c^7}{\hbar G^2} = 4.644 \times 10^{113} \text{ J m}^{-3} = 2.89 \times 10^{123} \text{ GeV m}^{-3} \quad \textit{Planck energy density}$$

$$T_{Pl} = \frac{E_{Pl}}{k_B} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{k_B^2 G}} = 1.416785(71) \times 10^{32} \text{ K} \quad \textit{Planck temperature}$$

Source: [3]

A.4 Gaussian statistics

Approximation / Confidence level

1σ 68.3 %

2σ 95.5 %

3σ 99.7 %

Source: [6]

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